

Mapping the Semantics of the Street: A VLM-Driven Geospatial Analysis in Fatih, Istanbul

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Abstract

This study presents a Vision Language Model (VLM)-driven framework for scalable semantic mapping of urban streetscapes in Fatih, Istanbul. Street-view imagery from Mapillary (116,696 images) is transformed into structured GeoAI descriptions using Qwen3-VL 4B Instruct, then jointly encoded with the source images via Qwen3-VL-Embedding 2B to produce multimodal embeddings. Unsupervised clustering ($k=3$) of the embedding space yields three interpretable urban typologies: residential neighborhoods, heritage-tourism pedestrian zones, and major traffic corridors. The clusters exhibit geographic coherence, with 88.4% of the traffic-corridor cluster overlapping with OpenStreetMap highway features; additionally, 42.1% of capture sequences span multiple clusters, confirming that the groupings reflect semantic transitions rather than camera artifacts. The framework demonstrates that VLM-derived multimodal embeddings can produce meaningful spatial structure without manual labeling, offering a scalable foundation for GeoAI-based urban analytics.

Keywords: street-view imagery, vision language models, multimodal embeddings, urban semantics, GeoAI

1. Introduction

Street-view imagery (SVI) can provide a rich observational layer for urban analytics, yet extracting actionable insights from such data remains challenging with conventional geographic information system (GIS) workflows and traditional analytical methods. Recent advances in Large Language Models (LLMs) (Shingleton and Basiri 2025; Ning et al. 2025; Zhang et al. 2025; He, Nie, and Ma 2025) and Vision Language Models (VLMs) (Z. Li et al. 2024; Danish et al. 2025) offer significant

Published in “Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Geospatial Artificial Intelligence (GeoAI 2026) – Oral Presentation Papers”, edited by Haosheng Huang and Nico Van de Weghe, GeoAI 2026, 3-6 June 2026, Ghent, Belgium.

This contribution underwent single-blind peer review based on the extended abstract.

potential for geospatial artificial intelligence (GeoAI). By generating human-like descriptions of street scenes, these models can transform raw SVI into semantically dense, interpretable text and can serve as scalable proxies for expert annotation of built environment attributes. Prior studies have reported measurable alignment between model-based streetscape assessments, suggesting that VLM outputs can approximate expert-coded constructs at scale (Perez and Fusco 2025; Zhou, Zhang, and Zhu 2025).

Understanding street-level urban environments at scale is essential for evidence-based urban planning, heritage preservation, walkability assessment, and equitable resource allocation (Biljecki and Ito 2021). Conventional approaches rely on either coarse-grained land-use classifications that miss fine-grained experiential qualities (Ogawa et al. 2024), or labor-intensive expert audits that cannot scale beyond small study areas (Koo, Guhathakurta, and Botchwey 2022). A scalable method that captures the semantic richness of streetscapes, including how streets look, feel, and function, would enable planners and researchers to diagnose urban conditions, track neighborhood change, and compare districts systematically. VLM-based approaches offer a promising path toward this goal, yet their capacity to produce geographically coherent and interpretable urban typologies from street-view imagery remains underexplored.

In this study, we focus on one of Istanbul’s most historically stratified and socio-spatially complex districts, Fatih (Keyder 1999; Biehl 2015). We first use a VLM to produce structured, GeoAI-oriented descriptions for each image, and then derive multimodal embeddings by jointly encoding the imagery and the generated descriptions. In doing so, we introduce a compact GeoAI framework for mapping “street semantics” in Fatih. Building on the efficacy of embeddings in geolocalization (Bicakci, Shingleton, and Basiri 2025), our main objective is to examine whether the joint distribution of VLM-derived images and descriptions in an embedding vector space yields meaningful, geographically coherent structure, specifically whether it gives rise to interpretable spatial clusters when projected back into geographic space.

2. Data

We collected SVI uploaded within the administrative boundaries of Istanbul’s Fatih district from the Mapillary platform (Mapillary 2026), yielding a dataset of approximately 130,000 images. Each image is associated with geocoordinates, latitude and longitude, which enables spatial visualization of the learned semantic structure from SVI.

Because Mapillary consists entirely of community contributed content, the dataset exhibits substantial variation in glare, partial view, underexposure, occlusion, and blur. To address this, we used the VLM to assess whether each image was suitable for analysis and excluded those deemed unusable. The model was prompted to flag images with severe occlusion, extreme underexposure (nighttime/shadows), or motion blur. After this filtering step, a total of 116,696 images were retained and used in all analyses in this work.

3. Methodology

The methodology is implemented entirely using open-source libraries and openly available models. Our workflow consists of three main stages: GeoAI-oriented description generation, multimodal embedding generation, and clustering.

3.1. GeoAI-Oriented VLM Descriptions

For each image, we used the Qwen3-VL 4B Instruct (Bai et al. 2025) model to generate a JSON-structured GeoAI domain description. The prompting strategy emphasized urban spatial semantics such as land-use character, street type, semantic tags, place activity cues, and high-level streetscape quality as well as scene narrative (see Figure 1 for the full prompt structure). These descriptions capture not only objects but also the overall atmosphere of the scene, and architectural character.

3.2. Multimodal Embeddings

We paired each image with the GeoAI domain specific descriptions generated by the VLM and used the Qwen3-VL Embedding 2B model (M. Li et al. 2026) to construct multimodal embedded representations. Using the model’s full output size, each image-text pair is mapped to an embedding vector $z_i \in \mathbb{R}^{2048}$. This procedure yields a shared representation that encodes semantic context by jointly leveraging the visual content and the accompanying description. This model processes the image-text pair as a single multimodal input and produces a unified embedding that aligns visual cues directly with their semantic narratives. We then used these embeddings as the primary feature space for unsupervised clustering. Because the text is derived from the image, joint encoding may amplify semantics; future work will compare image-only, text-only, and joint embeddings.

3.3. Clustering

We clustered the embedding vectors into three groups, fixing $k = 3$ after an internal validity sweep over $k \in \{2, \dots, 10\}$ using MiniBatchKMeans (Pedregosa et al. 2011) and standard indices computed on a random subset of up to 5,000 samples. Quantitative metrics supported the choice of $k = 3$, as can be seen in Table 1. The Silhouette Coefficient (Rousseeuw 1987) peaked at $k = 3$ (0.1105) and the Calinski-Harabasz (CH) index (Caliński and Harabasz 1974) was maximized at $k = 3$ (497.93), indicating the strongest separation and compactness for a coarse-grained typology. While the Davies-Bouldin index (Davies and Bouldin 2009) suggested $k = 8$ for finer granularity, we selected $k = 3$ to prioritize macro-scale interpretability, consistent with the Silhouette and CH peaks. Figure 2 visualizes both options, demonstrating the clear separation at $k = 3$ alongside the more nuanced substructures revealed at $k = 8$.

	$k = 2$	$k = 3$	$k = 4$	$k = 5$	$k = 6$	$k = 7$	$k = 8$	$k = 9$	$k = 10$
Silhouette \uparrow	0.091	0.111	0.083	0.089	0.070	0.081	0.078	0.073	0.065
CH Index \uparrow	416.3	497.9	427.7	370.6	344.3	293.7	310.2	268.3	269.0
Davies-B. \downarrow	3.140	2.573	2.704	2.728	2.591	2.764	2.498	2.895	2.715

Table 1: Internal clustering validation metrics.

System Prompt:

```
You are a GeoAI specialist analyzing street-level imagery for urban spatial analytics research.
Your task is to extract geographically meaningful features that support:
- Spatial clustering and pattern detection
- Urban morphology analysis
- Place character and semantic neighborhood mapping
- Walkability and urban design quality assessment

OUTPUT: A single JSON object describing the scene's SPATIAL and URBAN characteristics.
SCHEMA:
{
  "scene_narrative": "<80-120 words describing the urban scene focusing on spatial layout, land
    use character, and built environment qualities>",
  "land_use_character": {
    "primary": "residential|commercial|mixed_use|institutional|industrial|recreational|
      historic_cultural|transportation|open_space",
    "secondary": "<same options or null>",
    "intensity": "low|medium|high"
  },
  "urban_morphology": {
    "street_type": "arterial|collector|local|pedestrian|alley|plaza|waterfront_promenade",
    "enclosure_ratio": "low|medium|high",
    "building_setback": "zero|minimal|moderate|large",
    "block_pattern": "grid|organic|irregular|cul_de_sac|unknown"
  },
  "streetscape_elements": {
    "sidewalk_quality": "absent|poor|fair|good|excellent",
    "street_trees": "none|sparse|moderate|dense",
    "street_furniture": ["bench", "lighting", "bollard", "planter", "trash_bin", "bus_shelter"],
    "facade_transparency": "low|medium|high",
    "signage_density": "none|low|medium|high"
  },
  "mobility_infrastructure": {
    "modes_visible": ["pedestrian", "bicycle", "private_vehicle", "bus", "tram", "ferry"],
    "parking_presence": "none|on_street|off_street|both",
    "transit_stops": true/false,
    "crosswalk_type": "none|unmarked|marked|signalized|raised"
  },
  "place_character": {
    "dominant_activity": "transit|shopping|dining|tourism|residential_quiet|mixed_active|
      industrial|unknown",
    "temporal_markers": "day|night|dawn|dusk|unknown",
    "human_presence": "none|sparse|moderate|crowded",
    "visual_complexity": "low|medium|high"
  },
  "historic_cultural_elements": {
    "architectural_period": "ottoman|byzantine|republic_era|modern|mixed|unknown",
    "heritage_features": ["mosque", "minaret", "historic_wall", "fountain", "
      traditional_shopfront", "cobblestone", "none"],
    "cultural_signifiers": ["turkish_script", "religious_symbol", "traditional_craft", "none"]
  },
  "environmental_quality": {
    "greenery_coverage": "none|minimal|moderate|abundant",
    "sky_visibility": "low|medium|high",
    "cleanliness": "poor|fair|good",
    "maintenance_level": "neglected|fair|well_maintained"
  },
  "spatial_safety_cues": {
    "lighting_adequacy": "poor|fair|good|unknown",
    "sightlines": "obstructed|partial|clear",
    "enclosure_feeling": "exposed|balanced|confined",
    "activity_level": "deserted|low|moderate|active"
  },
  "geo_context": {
    "topography": "flat|gentle_slope|steep|unknown",
    "water_visibility": true/false,
    "landmark_proximity": ["none", "mosque", "historic_gate", "waterfront", "major_transit", "
      market"],
    "neighborhood_type": "historic_core|transitional|peripheral|waterfront|unknown"
  },
  "image_quality": {
    "usable_for_analysis": true/false,
    "issues": ["blur", "occlusion", "overexposure", "underexposure", "partial_view", "none"]
  },
  "semantic_tags": ["<5-10 keywords for embedding/clustering, e.g.: historic, pedestrian,
    commercial, quiet, tourist, residential, busy, narrow, waterfront, religious>"]
}
```

User Prompt:

```
Analyze this street-level image from Istanbul's Fatih district for GeoAI urban analytics
research.

Focus on:
1. What type of urban place is this? (land use, character)
2. What is the spatial quality? (enclosure, walkability, design)
3. What semantic themes define this location? (for clustering)

Return ONLY the JSON object following the schema. No other text.
```

Figure 1: The system prompt configuration and JSON schema enforced for VLM description generation.

Figure 2: Two-dimensional projection of the multimodal embedding space, comparing the selected coarse-grained partition at $k = 3$ (left) with the finer granularity suggested by the DB index at $k = 8$ (right).

4. Results and Discussion

After following the steps described in the Methodology section, Figures 3 and 4 show that a clear three cluster typology emerges across Fatih.

The first cluster groups ordinary neighborhoods that are predominantly residential and used by the district’s local residents. As can be seen, these scenes cover nearly all side streets and residential areas of the district. Semantic tags such as “narrow”, “residential”, and “commercial” frequently appear in this cluster, reflecting street morphology and everyday land-use cues. The second cluster is associated with scenes that contain cues consistent with historical and tourist environments, and it often includes pedestrian streetscapes. Semantic tags such as “tourism”, “historic”, “quiet”, and “religious” frequently appear in this cluster, suggesting that the embedding space separates locations with distinct cultural and pedestrian place signatures. The third cluster is visually concentrated along major corridors and is distinguished by wider roads and traffic-dominant environments. As a quantitative proxy, the locations of 26,484 of the 29,968 images assigned to this cluster (88.4%) coincide with OpenStreetMap (OSM) features tagged as highways, supporting the interpretation that the cluster reflects the district’s primary transportation infrastructure.

Notably, while Cluster 2 and Cluster 3 remain semantically distinct, they occur in close spatial proximity along the southern coastal edge. Cluster 2 captures nearby pedestrian sidewalks by the sea, while Cluster 3 identifies the adjacent highway only a few meters away. This fine separation suggests that the VLM-derived representations can distinguish micro-scale transitions in street function from visual perspective.

Furthermore, quantitative analysis confirms that 42.1% of individual capture sequences span multiple clusters. This indicates that the grouping is driven by shifting semantic contexts (e.g., transitions between street types) rather than static camera parameters or visual artifacts.

The emerging typology aligns with established urban morphology concepts: the residential-commercial

Figure 3: Representative examples for each cluster.

Figure 4: Spatial distribution of three semantic clusters.

fabric of Cluster 1 corresponds to what urban theorists term the “ordinary city” matrix, while the heritage-tourism axis of Cluster 2 and the arterial infrastructure of Cluster 3 mirror functional zoning patterns observed in mixed-use historic districts. This alignment suggests that VLM-derived embeddings can recover latent urban structure that would otherwise require labor-intensive field surveys or expert classification. From a practical standpoint, such a scalable semantic mapping capability could support urban planners in identifying areas requiring pedestrian safety interventions, heritage conservation prioritization, or green infrastructure investment.

Several limitations should be noted. First, cluster semantics are assigned post hoc and have not been validated against local expert knowledge; future work will include stratified manual checks and independent ground-truth labels. Second, concepts such as place character and urban quality are culturally situated: VLM descriptors applied to non-Western urban settings may reproduce Western-centric interpretations inherited from training data. Future work will address this through prompt variations, local expert review, and cross-city comparisons. Third, the representativeness of the clusters is constrained by the spatial and temporal coverage of Mapillary’s crowdsourced imagery, which may under-represent certain neighborhoods or time periods.

Overall, the embeddings of the images, combined with the descriptions produced by the VLM, demonstrate that it is possible to produce an interpretable and meaningful semantic atlas without manual labeling, providing a scalable foundation for evidence-based urban analytics and further GeoAI studies.

5. Conclusion

A new VLM-based GeoAI perspective is presented for district-scale semantic mapping in Fatih, Istanbul, which is the city’s oldest historical area and a capital for diverse cultures over centuries. SVI downloaded from Mapillary is transformed into GeoAI descriptions using Qwen3-VL 4B Instruct, and these descriptions are then combined with the images to produce embeddings using Qwen3-VL-Embedding 2B. By clustering the embedded representations, an interpretable typology is obtained. These clusters correspond, respectively, to everyday local streets and living environments, heritage tourism and pedestrian-oriented historic places, and major arterials and modern roads with dense traffic. This street semantics approach reveals Fatih’s urban structure without requiring manual annotation, offering a scalable alternative to expert-driven audits for characterizing urban environments. Future studies will incorporate rigorous ablation studies comparing image-only, text-only, and joint embeddings, address potential biases within Mapillary data, and validate the framework through cross-city comparisons and local expert review.

Acknowledgements: The authors thank the open-source software community and resource providers that enabled this study, including Mapillary, Qwen, and the models used in our experiments. The authors acknowledge the support from the UK Research and Innovation Future Leaders Fellowships “Indicative Data: Extracting 3D Models of Cities from Unavailability and Degradation of Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS)” [MR/S01795X/2] and “Missing Data as Useful Data” [MR/Y011856/1], AI Metascience Fellowship “Generative AI and the Future of Research Software Engineering” [UKRI2599], and the Alan Turing Institute-DSO partnership project on “Multi-Lingual and Multi-Modal Location Information Extraction”.

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